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Biases of News Media Producers

Work package 3 – Deliverable 3.5

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1. Executive summary

This report investigates forms of biases encountered by news producers (here: mainly professional journalists working for news organisations) in their daily news work. The report is based on a survey with over 60 international journalists, recruited across different organisational contexts, nationalities, levels of seniority and years of experience. The approach is deliberately open to identify biases and general perceptions of coverage of migration beyond specific national contexts. This approach acknowledges that public discourses on migration are often politically instrumentalised and shaped by journalistic and non-journalistic news sources, e.g. social media platforms. The survey addressed news producers' views of general biases in the news and news-making practices, their respective national and political contexts, the conditions and shortcomings of covering migration in particular, as well as probing the potential of tools associated with open-source intelligence (OSINT), verification and fact-checking as measures to counter such biases.

Respondents were recruited through snowball sampling in professional networks of journalists, social media posts and professional associations without restricting the sample to only journalists who cover migration. The survey was answered fully by 60 respondents, with slightly more female than male participants, with many responses from Germany and Austria, apart from other European and few non-European countries. The sample reflects a focus on early to mid-career journalists with more than 4 years of experience in news organisations. The survey consisted of three main parts: 1) biases emerging from editorial and news routines 2) biases in relation to covering migration topics specifically and how these could be mitigated; and 3) knowledge of and usefulness of OSINT tools and techniques to mitigate biases and misinformation in general and in relation to migration topics.

Core findings of the report and survey

Editorial gatekeeping and journalists' positionality shape coverage

- The authority of editorial gatekeeping exerts a strong influence on reporting and framing, including which stories get covered, which get visibility on a medium's platforms, down to specific words and terminologies journalists use when writing. This exacerbates formulaic and trite framing of migration along episodic rather than structurally analytic patterns.
- There is a gap between journalists' perception of general coverage bias (in their own and other news organisations) and the recognition of their own biases. They also consider their personal views as the least influential aspect in reporting, while personal background and interests inform their choice of perspective and sources for a given story.

Countering national 'threat frames' and negativity biases

- Most journalists agree that national coverage of migration mainly focuses on topics such as the economy, border control, and social problems, restating 'threat frames' that are mainly negative. This is also a sourcing problem, since prioritising political voices in coverage allows these negative frames to reappear. Journalists recognise the need to have migrants' perspectives in the news to change such narratives, and see greater diversity of newsroom workforces as a central conduit to achieve this.

OSINT tools and verification remain a promising but specialised domain

- Journalists recognise that computational OSINT techniques and tools can be an important addition to their skillset and toolbox to reduce time spent on research and verification of facts and reduce biases. Time constraints for learning such techniques and the lack of wider institutional support for including them in editorial workflows pose a main obstacle, though, to their implementation.

2. About DEMINE

DEMINE goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyze the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.

- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers, and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarization and radicalization to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarized world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

In European societies, the growing perception of polarisation between ideological camps has become an increasing matter of concern for societal cohesion and democratic decision-making. Especially global issues such as climate change, the COVID-19 pandemic or migration are difficult to contain and understand within national contexts and are often reflected in news coverage as episodic events that obscure the larger underlying structural patterns and dependencies. Moreover, political and public discourse has shifted to online and social media platforms, with their own incentives to prioritise controversial or propagandistic content dissemination that elides the established routines of professional news work in journalistic organisations. News producers are no longer technically or professionally limited to journalists, and a widened public domain of discourse poses challenges to established professional norms and procedures, not least since audiences diversify and favour sources for news consumption based on individual preferences.

The public critique of news media being biased towards expert and elite sources is echoed in a plethora of alternative news sites, some of which are deliberately confrontational, some of which attempt to diversify public opinion. The issue of migration into Europe as well as instrumentalisation poses a specific challenge for news producers, as the structural political conditions of addressing migration are strongly shaped by the political agenda of national parties and governments. With coverage being strongly informed by conventional sources dominating the discourse and migration being often framed as a problem to civic management, as a ‘threat’ to cultural homogeneity, economic stability, or the larger structural issues of global migration flows are difficult to reflect in news-based communication. Biases emerging in coverage of migration can have psychological origins, emerge from lack of knowledge about or contact with migrant communities or be situated in news making routines that have traditions in a pre-social media environment, relying overtly on individual sources. Lastly, the new possibilities of technologically identifying biases and verifying information remain expert skills that are not yet widely established in the journalistic profession.

This report focuses on identifying and addressing the biases of news media producers, emphasising both technology-driven and individual factors that influence reporting in relation to migration. It reveals the structural constraints of news media professionals to confront known and acknowledged biases, as well as detailing obstacles to enhancing the integrity and accuracy of their work. A central topic of the report is an evaluation of how computational tools and Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) techniques designed to assist in identifying and correcting bias in media content are currently used and what obstacles stand in the way of their wider implementation. The report provides detailed insights into how these tools can be integrated into daily journalistic practices, offering practical strategies and opportunities for news producers to reduce biases and improve the credibility of their reporting to counter public distrust.

4. State of the Art – Media Biases, Reporting on Migration and OSINT in Journalism

Concerns over media bias are related to declining trust in news worldwide with few exceptions. Some of this growing distrust is related to perceptions that the media often tend to favour one side of a story, or are often sensationalist and inaccurate (Banerjee et al., 2023). While most studies examine this perspective from the audience side (Kalfeli et al., 2025), including also strategies by younger audiences to deal with ‘information cacophony’ and overload from multiple sources (Cotter and Thorson, 2022), it remains equally relevant to investigate how journalists see the media landscape, reflect on their own work, and identify possibilities for changes of established routines to regain public trust. Previous studies have shown consistent patterns in how news is produced, such as a focus on negative framing and reliance on official sources. Yet, fewer studies provide insights on how aware journalists are of the processes driving these patterns (Verleyen and Beckers, 2023).

Different research areas have investigated bias in journalism. Media studies, cognitive psychology, political science, and communication theory have examined whether journalists apply the normative standards of neutrality and objectivity that newsrooms claim to uphold. In all areas, however, there is no single definition for media bias. The term is applied, for instance, to news that distorts reality, favours one side of a conflict, and contains personal opinions of journalists (Entman, 2007). Definitions tend to share the idea, though, that news bias has a consistent pattern and is not an isolated error that influences how audiences understand an event (Rodrigo-Ginés et al., 2024).

Several types of bias documented in the literature informed the survey design in this study. These included *gatekeeping bias*, also described as selection or agenda bias, concerning which stories editors and journalists decide to cover (D'Alessio and Allen, 2000); *framing bias*, which looks at the influences on how a story is told and how events are presented (Entman, 2007); *language bias*, covering the words journalists use, the quotes they select, and how they contextualise facts (Lazaridou and Krestel, 2016); *source selection bias*, which examines the tendency to rely on institutionally accessible sources or those that confirm an existing angle (Rodrigo-Ginés et al., 2024); and *confirmation bias*, which explores whether journalists seek out information challenging their initial angle, and the effect of *deadline pressures* on the news-making process (Christian, 2017).

These types of bias are especially visible in the coverage of migration. Research consistently shows that migration news is framed through lenses of security or crisis, frequently using language that depicts migration as dangerous and as a threat to (national) culture and economy (Seiger, F. et al., 2025). While migrants are the primary subjects of reporting, they are rarely used as direct sources. Instead, political and institutional sources dominate the narrative, obscuring the voice of migrant communities (Thorbjørnsrud, 2015). The possibility to change this one-sided journalistic practice, though, could help reduce the negative frames in the news by including migrants in news stories as active agents (Verleyen and Beckers, 2023), that would "[allow] journalists to expose inequalities, provide meaningful context, and amplify underrepresented perspectives" (Kalfeli et al., 2025, p. 17). By changing such practices, "media can also function as a powerful ally in challenging public prejudices, sparking informed debate, and promoting positive, human-centered narratives about stigmatized minorities (...)" (ibid., p. 4).

To assist in countering biases, Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) frameworks provide techniques and tools to increase accuracy of reporting and reveal misinformation, fake news and 'network propaganda' disseminated on social media and the Web (Benkler et al., 2018). They work through the collection, analysis, and use of publicly available information for investigative purposes, help to ensure accuracy (Le Deuff et al., 2026), and build transparent investigations. With legacies in cybersecurity and criminal investigations (Khera et al., 2024; Sampson, 2017), newer approaches in this field favour the label OSINV (open-source investigations) to foreground the journalistic collaboration with OSINT communities, developers and investigators (Dodds et al., 2025; Charlton et al., 2024). The wider societal relevance of OSINT/V communities together with news organisations and civil society organisations (CSO) lies in their ability to create "trust-building infrastructure" for public discourses where the tools, analysis procedures and datasets used in investigations can be made transparent for audiences (Zamith, 2023). When used together with Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Ganguly, 2022; Gioni et al., 2023) OSINT/V techniques are nowadays possible to scale to investigate large data sets and retrieve patterns at significantly lower costs than a few years ago. Such newer approaches are breaking the expert circles of journalism and are especially relevant in conflict zones and war coverage, where a lot of citizen-generated footage needs to be verified (Hamouda, 2023). On a broader scale OSINT/V techniques are employed by investigations of online misinformation investigations by institutions such as the Center for Monitoring, Analysis and Strategy (CeMAS) or correctiv (Germany), Forensic Architecture (UK) or Bellingcat (The Netherlands), apart from notable OSINT and fact-checking units at *The Guardian*, the *BBC*, or *The New York Times*.

In summary, while the study of media biases is established in journalism studies, the new challenges emerging from transnational (and highly polarising) subjects such as migration as well as the growing

threats of online disinformation, new public opinion influencers and changing dynamics of a “hybrid media system” (Chadwick, 2013) put established journalistic routines under pressure. At the same time, OSINT/V approaches and techniques remain a rather specialist field of countering such biases. The purpose of this study therefore is to investigate how potential 'hierarchies of influences' on new-making routines at the level of individual journalistic practices and the level of news organisations (Ferrucci and Kuhn, 2022) can profit from a stronger integration with collaborative open-source frameworks and techniques to compensate for resource constraints as well as allowing new modes of reporting reflecting complexities of global issues such as migration coverage in less biased ways.

5. Methodology

This report draws on insights from an **online survey** among journalists. The decision to conduct a survey derives from the deliverable's aims: to identify bias among news media producers at both the technology-driven and individual level, encourage reflection on how to mitigate bias, and explore ways in which OSINT techniques assist in that matter, with a special regard to migration reporting. As these questions concern journalists' own attitudes, perceptions and practices, they are best addressed by approaching them directly through a self-reported survey format. Surveys are often employed to explore “journalists' perceptions of themselves, their work, and their surroundings” (Molyneux & Zamith, 2022, p. 155). The choice of method was further guided by the online survey's capacity to reach a wide audience across different places and news contexts. Special emphasis was put on including a broad range of journalists and news producers to participate, with diverse perspectives on how they perceive bias and seek to address it in their reporting. The survey format also lowers the threshold for participation, which is an important consideration given that journalists today experience precarious working conditions, face public criticism and political agitation, and have to cope with economic pressures in the news industries, which, taken together, limit their time and resources to participate in research.

The **planning and execution of the survey** generally drew on Bryman (2012) for the design of surveys and Molyneux & Zamith's (2022) specific recommendations for surveying journalists. The questionnaire was created with Qualtrics, which offered secure data handling and easy distribution via link. The survey was designed to take a maximum of ten minutes to complete. It opened with an outline of the research aims, the study's authors, information about data processing and funding background of DEMINE. The survey consisted of four main sections.

- In the first section, the survey introduced general aspects of possible influence on journalistic practice. Respondents were asked to evaluate the extent to which certain biases identified in the literature impacted their everyday decision-making, work routines and editorial environment. Since biases are analytically quite distinct and empirically latent properties of news coverage, the questions were formed in a way to ask for agreement/disagreement with certain statements that ex post revealed the latency of biases and journalists' awareness of them. Additionally, the significance of personal background in relation to journalistic practice (i.e., their positionality) was addressed (See the full questionnaire in the Appendix).
- In the second section, the survey focused on the coverage of migration specifically, foregrounding journalists' own perceptions of this coverage in relation to the national political context where they are affiliated. Participants evaluated how migration is reported in their country and within their own news organisation and what improvements or changes to this coverage they would favour.

- The third section addressed digital tools used in reporting. To clarify the subsequent questions, a short explanation of the term OSINT (Open-Source Intelligence) was provided. Participants then assessed their experience with different tools and how frequently they used them. Further, this section sought to identify primary obstacles to the adoption of digital tools and the contexts in which journalists considered them worthwhile and helpful.
- In the fourth section, participants were asked to provide information on their professional and demographic backgrounds, to allow a better interpretation of their responses in relation to age, professional status, main field of reporting and type of organisation. Optionally, respondents could provide their emails to be informed of the survey results.

The design of survey questions needed to reflect a variety of journalistic roles and contexts with each section briefly introducing the topic. The sections on general journalistic practice and migration coverage used five-point Likert-scale items to assess participants' attitudes towards given statements, ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). In all sections, single and multiple-choice questions were included as supplementary items. Additionally, parts of the questionnaire incorporated open-ended questions, allowing free-text responses on individual perceptions of participants (Bryman, 2012), especially the sections addressing migration coverage and digital tools to provide additional context for analysis. Wording of questions and scales remained consistent throughout the survey to improve understanding (Molyneux & Zamith, 2022).

The **questionnaire was pre-tested** among ten individuals with a background in journalism before public release. These answers are not included in the results. The pre-testing provided extensive feedback on overall understanding and survey structure, question wording, and the estimated time to complete the survey. Based on these responses, the survey was shortened, the wording of items was refined, and short introductions to all four sections were added.

Our **sampling strategy** was designed to encompass a diverse range of journalistic perspectives on news reporting practices. Journalists from all areas were encouraged to participate in the survey. Thus, no restrictions were placed on media type, professional role, career stage, or geographic location. The sampling was not intended to be representative, instead it prioritised inclusivity to reflect a wide variety of journalistic contexts. Eligible respondents were recruited via a snowball method. Initial contacts were asked to disseminate the survey link within their network of journalists. This strategy allowed us to address the above-mentioned challenges to conduct research on journalists in a time-efficient manner.

To establish initial contact points, we first reached out to organisations with journalists' contacts. This included journalist associations as well as non-governmental organisations and groups related to journalism. They were asked to share the survey with their journalism communities via newsletters, social media platforms, or alike. Simultaneously, we contacted media outlets across Europe, asking them to distribute the questionnaire to their staff. Emphasis was put on English-speaking outlets due to the language of the survey. When responses remained low, we used our professional networks to disseminate the survey to eligible journalists.

The **distribution** was primarily administered via email from an Aarhus University domain, and all responses were securely stored on GDPR-compliant servers of Aarhus University to safeguard the joint data handling agreement of the DEMINE consortium. Results in this report are presented in aggregate to not reveal any individual participant's responses.

Due to the applied snowballing approach across several stages, an overall response rate is not available, as we cannot determine the total number of journalists who received the link. The survey was open from 03.02.2026 until 31.03.2026.

6. Results

The survey reached journalists from across 21 countries, representing a geographically diverse sample. Journalists from Germany and Austria made up the largest share of respondents. The majority of participants stated to be between 25 and 34 years of age. When it comes to professional experience, the largest group reported four to seven years in the field, followed by those with one to three years and a smaller group with eight to fifteen years of experience. This points to a sample weighted towards mid-career journalists while capturing both early-career and more experienced journalists. Most respondents identified as staff journalists/full-time employees, with a rather small group identifying as freelancing/self-employed. Politics was the most cited area of coverage.

6.1 Demographics

The survey received responses from across 21 countries. In total, 104 participants opened the survey, of whom 74 started, and **60 respondents completed all the questions in the survey**. In the results we considered all replies, even if the respondent did not answer all questions. The majority are from Germany (32%) and Austria (28%), followed by Denmark, Belgium, Hungary, and the United Kingdom. Respondents are also based in the Netherlands, Norway, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Poland, the Czech Republic, Italy, Albania, and several countries outside Europe, including Brazil, Colombia, Peru, Ghana, Kenya, and Thailand. Since nationality was not a variable for the survey, the results capture a broad insight on different forms of biases impacting migration coverage in respect to working routines and organisational contexts.

Slightly more women responded to the survey compared to men (55% women/43% men), with one respondent identifying as non-binary. **The sample is predominantly young:** Almost three-quarters of respondents (72%) are between 25 and 34 years old, and 10% are under 25 years, with only 18% of respondents being 35 and older.

Journalists' age

Total number of responses: n=60.

The largest group of respondents has between four and fifteen years of experience in journalism (61%), followed by those with less than three years (33%) or more than fifteen years (5%). Over half of the participants (52%) are staff journalists or full-time employees. The number is followed by freelancers and the self-employed (20%), interns/trainees (15%), and part-time employees (12%).

Journalists' years of experience

Total number of responses: n=60.

Most respondents work for national news outlets (37%) or international news organisations (25%), and a minority works for local and regional outlets (13%). Politics is the most common reporting focus (38%), followed by economy and business (12%), culture and arts (10%), and migration and human rights (7%). The remaining respondents cover other areas, including local news, investigative journalism, environment, and technology. They mainly work in organisations with 500 or more employees (40%), or in smaller newsrooms with either between 51 and 200 employees (17%) or smaller organisations (35%).

6.2 Main Factor's Influencing Journalists' News Work

The first part of the questionnaire aims to understand the main factors influencing journalists' decision-making when producing news, covering main challenges in news work routines, their opinion on whether a journalist's background is relevant to shaping the story, and whether journalists should declare personal perspectives when reporting on an issue. For the first two questions, respondents were given multiple options ranging from personal views to editorial priorities and asked to choose from strongly agree to strongly disagree on each of them. For the other two questions, respondents could choose at what level they believe the answer to the question was, respectively, important/influential or not important/less relevant.

6.2.1 The Authority of Editorial Gatekeeping

The findings indicate that factors influencing journalists' reporting process are a combination of editorial decisions, time constraints, and, to a smaller extent, personal decisions. Among these, editorial influence emerges as the most significant factor throughout different stages of news production. A large majority of respondents recognise that editorial priorities somewhat influence which stories are covered (87%) and which get visibility (90%). This level of agreement is higher than on other influencing factors, reinforcing the role of editorial structures in how news is produced. This confirms a strong 'gatekeeping bias', when editors hold power in selecting which stories are considered 'newsworthy' and will be shown to the audiences, and the topics they are not going to write about (D'Alessio and Allen, 2000). When comparing these responses, a significant correlation

emerges. Journalists who feel the strongest editorial influence also report the highest pressure from deadlines.

The operational constraints of the newsroom also appear to influence news sources. Nearly 72% of respondents agree that they tend to rely on sources that are easier to reach or institutionally recognised, with 19% “strongly” and 53% “somewhat” agreeing. This ‘source selection bias’ is likely driven by time pressures. **By prioritising established institutional voices, journalists (inadvertently or deliberately) limit the range of perspectives in a story**, which can lead to a limited diversity when explaining a situation or event (Rodrigo-Ginés et al., 2024).

Aspects that have the most influence on journalists’ reporting

Total number of responses: n=74.

The impact of the editorial line is also present in the writing process. Around two-thirds of respondents (67%) agree that **editorial line influences word choices and terminology** used when writing a story. Nearly 49% of those who agree with this statement work in the field of politics or migration/human rights. Recent debates around language used in conflict and political reporting exemplify this dynamic, particularly regarding words and terms restricted or discouraged by news organisations. Although it is common for news organisations to establish style guidelines, journalists have reported that these may be applied in ways that shape coverage towards one side of a conflict. In the UK, former BBC journalists went to court, alleging restrictions on employees covering the war, and allegations that employees were dismissed for raising concerns about impartiality. Although debates over asymmetries in coverage of conflict or political reporting are not new, they show how news companies still try to maintain claims of neutrality and avoid perceptions of ideological bias.

6.2.2 The Influence of Journalists’ Positionality and Social Media

When asked about personal challenges that influence reporting, there are contrasting answers on similar topics. While respondents were cautious to admit that their personal opinion directly influences their reporting, responses were higher in agreeing on the **influence of their personal background on a story**. 70% of respondents believe a journalist’s background (ethnicity, gender, economic status) is “very” or “moderate influential” in shaping a story. This suggests that while journalists still strive for the professional ideal of objectivity, they also recognise that positionality, who they are and from where they look at a story, is an influential factor in how news is produced.

Finally, while editorial priorities remain as the main influence, the results show a significant shift towards the importance of metrics in reporting. Although only 8% “strongly agree” that they change

their stories for the audience, 49% “somewhat agree” that they **adjust reporting to align with audience interests and social media trends**. Research shows an increase in journalists adapting content to fit into platforms’ logics, highlighting conflicts between topics of public interest and strategies that are mainly metrics-oriented (Salamon et al., 2026).

6.3 Journalists’ Views on Migration Coverage

The second part of the survey focuses on journalists’ perceptions of migration coverage. Participants were asked to evaluate statements regarding how the topic of migration is reported in their own news organisation and, more broadly, in the national media of the country where they are based. The section also included two open-ended questions. One question asked for how migration *should* be covered, according to their personal and professional viewpoint, and a second question allowed for adding personal comments and assessments. Results of this section provide empirical support found also in the literature that **migration coverage often exhibits a frequent focus on negative frames and episodic events**, portraying immigrants as cultural and security threats (Eberl et al., 2018; Kalfeli et al., 2025; Verleyen et al., 2025).

6.3.1 The National Context: Security, Politics, and the "Threat Frame"

There is almost a consensus among respondents regarding the narrow focus of migration coverage at a national level. More than nine in ten journalists (93%) either “strongly” or “somewhat” agree that national coverage of migration primarily centres on crime, border control, and social problems. The focus on the violent narrative reinforces what scholars call the “threat frame” (Kalfeli et al., 2025), where the portrayal of migrants serves to consolidate stereotypes of them as a risk to society.

Migration coverage in the country where journalists are based

Total number of responses: n=66.

The prevalence of **negative narratives seems to be a structural problem in the media**. Only about a quarter of respondents (25%) “strongly” or “somewhat” agree that coverage has changed positively or become more balanced over the last years. Part of this lack of progress can be understood by journalists’ sourcing choices. Almost 82% of journalists believe that, to a certain extent, national coverage prioritises political rhetoric rather than the reality of the migrants and their community. As a result, while migrants are the subject of the stories, they are rarely the primary source. Instead, the narrative is shaped by official figures and political actors (Kalfeli et al., 2025).

6.3.2 The 'Institutional Exception': Divergent Views on Newsroom Bias

A significant finding in this study is the divergence between how journalists view the national coverage and how they evaluate the coverage of migration from their news organisation. Although they recognise systemic problems in the industry, they are less likely to acknowledge those same biases in their work environment.

While only 25% of respondents consider national migration news generally balanced, nearly double the number (45%) believe their newsrooms provide a balanced perspective. However, when asked about the general focus of topics, more than half of respondents (57%) admit that coverage in their news organisation also tends to focus on certain dominant themes such as security, politics and the economy, with limited diversity of viewpoints.

Migration coverage in journalists' news organisations

Total number of responses: n=63.

In general, responses reveal a certain level of neutrality when journalists are asked about their news organisation. In many of the statements, they would choose the option 'neither agree nor disagree' to evaluate the questions. When asked if the coverage of migration in their newsroom is mostly one-sided or heavily influenced by political parties, responses were divided. While a large part (48%) disagrees with the statement, more than half either acknowledged the political influence (28%) or preferred to remain neutral 28%.

A significant finding of this study is a perceived **discrepancy between individual and organisational pressures that shape reporting**, especially regarding the influence of social media. On an individual level, a majority of journalists acknowledged that they adjust their reporting to align with audience metrics and social media trends (56%), with 48% "somewhat" and 8% "strongly" agreeing. However, when evaluating their newsrooms susceptibility to the same pressure, responses diverge. The most frequent response was "neither agree nor disagree" (38%), and the agreement level was lower, with only 3% "strongly" and 24% somewhat agreeing with the influence of social media on news reporting priorities.

6.3.3 Journalists' Contributions to Migration Coverage

The survey invited journalists to reflect on **how to mitigate structural biases in covering migration** and to add further comments. In an analysis of the 58 responses, some recurring topics emerged: coverage should be more balanced and critical, independent of 'political agenda', and migrants should have a direct voice. To achieve such changes, many respondents pointed out that newsrooms should be more diverse in terms of the staff they employ.

Respondents emphasised that improving migration coverage requires a shift in the depth of narrative and reporting. Many argue that **news frequently lacks basic context** and that journalists must explain the power dynamics involved. This includes **failing to explain the structures that force migratory movements**, the political context in which migration happens and the root causes of displacement. There is a perceived need to be more critical when examining government decisions and not merely reporting them verbatim. There is also a perceived lack of historical (and sometimes colonial) perspectives that contribute to prejudices in the first place that contribute to a hostile environment towards migrants in society.

“Responsible coverage must interrogate structural factors: why do people migrate? What role do historical patterns of extraction, climate disruption, conflict, and inequality play? The coverage should examine policy frameworks critically assessing whether legal migration pathways exist, how asylum systems function in practice, and what enforcement mechanisms prioritize. Coverage should actively counter dehumanizing language, challenge statistical manipulation, and provide context for sensationalized incidents. This includes examining how different stakeholders—governments, civil society organizations, international bodies—frame migration issues and whose interests these framings serve.”

Danish journalist working with migration and human rights

A recurring theme was **the need for the media to move away from the “threat” frame that currently dominates news of migration**. Even though they had already evaluated this in the question before, respondents were especially critical of how migration in the news is instrumentalised by political actors, with some affirming that this amplifies far-right narratives. **By reporting on political rhetoric, the media often repeats frames that define migration exclusively as a security and economic problem to society** (Thorbjørnsrud, 2015). Journalists noted that this political focus is often also sustained by a ‘survivor bias’ in reporting, which is the tendency to focus only on those who successfully reached Europe, ignoring the stories of those trapped or lost in transit

Journalists emphasise that **reporting should shift from episodically framed crisis moments to a more human, in-depth and constructive reporting, putting migrants at the centre of the narrative**. Despite recognising the need for change in the reporting, journalists pointed to challenges in including migrants' voices, highlighting the lack of resources as a barrier:

“I would prefer if journalists talked to migrants and actively included them in news coverage. Oftentimes that is difficult though: small offices don't have translators or people that talk the language. Translation apps make conversations stale and slow. Interview partners are also challenging to manage when journalists are not connected in the specific communities.”

Young German journalist working with local news

As an alternative to this problem, respondents recommend engaging with contact grassroots organisations. The quote, however, highlights how newsroom structures and limitations can lead to oversimplification of a topic, and contribute to a continued “silence” of migrants in the news, as 53% of respondents recognise it occurs on a national level.

The responses suggest that **improving the content and frame of migration coverage also requires changes inside the newsrooms**. Journalists argued that a lack of diversity in editorial teams is an obstacle to balanced coverage. They emphasised the **need for representation of journalists with migrant backgrounds and diverse language skills**, to challenge stereotypical narratives and expand narrow and limited coverage.

The findings show that **journalists are aware of the different types of bias present in migration reporting and are highly critical of them**. However, they recognise that established newsrooms routines, also enforced through time constraints and reliance on official sources favour political narratives over narratives of migrants themselves. This creates a cycle where, **despite journalists' desire for change, the same recurring negative frames are reproduced**.

6.4 OSINT Tools in Journalistic Work

In the third part, we analyse the integration of OSINT (Open-source intelligence) tools in newsrooms and journalists' work. Journalists were asked about their knowledge and use of OSINT, and among a list of tools, they evaluated the most used tools, their frequency, and shared the main obstacles to using such verification techniques in news reporting. At the end, they were asked in an open-ended question to reflect on how digital tools could support more balanced reporting.

6.4.1 Journalists' use of OSINT tools

The survey indicates that **most respondents do not use OSINT as a primary resource in their daily reporting**. When asked to rate the importance of OSINT techniques for their work, only 7% described them as “extremely” and 19% as “very” important. The largest part of participants categorised them as “moderately” (34%) and “slightly” (34%) important. A further 7% reported that it is not relevant at all to their work.

In line with the results of the relevance of OSINT, most of those who report using it are limited to basic functions. **Google Maps is the most adopted tool**, with 85% of respondents reporting to have “good” or “extensive” experience. It is also the tool used most frequently, with 83% of respondents using it daily, weekly, or several times a month. **Consulting public databases appears as the second most integrated technique**, with 65% of respondents doing it regularly (daily, weekly, or several times a month). However, only half of the sample (49%) reports having a high level of experience.

More **specialised investigative techniques show the lowest level of experience and use**. Crowdsourcing information retrieval and web scraping are the methods with the least reported usage, with 50% of respondents stating they have never used the techniques. The lack of familiarity also reflects on its usage in newsrooms, with 48% and 37%, respectively, stating they have no experience with them. Similarly, web scraping tools for social media and tracing geolocation are methods with a low level of knowledge, with 37% of the journalists sharing that they have no experience with either.

Main obstacles to using news verification techniques

Total number of responses: n=59.

Journalists identify several obstacles to the low level of integration of OSINT tools in their work. Lack of training and knowledge of the tools is listed as the main barrier (63%), followed by limited editorial encouragement or institutional support (58%). They also report difficulty in integrating tools into existing workflows (42%) and time constraints (41%) as some of the limitations.

6.4.2 Journalists' View on The Role of Digital Tools for Balanced Reporting

The qualitative responses provide details on how journalists believe digital tools, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), can contribute to the production of more balanced reporting. Despite the limitations in the use of OSINT, journalists are positive about the ways these tools can be used to increase accuracy and transparency. Recurring topics include the advantages of verification and transparency of information, detection of language bias, and the possibility of saving time during the research process.

Verification and Transparency

Journalists identify digital tools as a primary way of ensuring that claims and statements, whether from news sources or social media, are based on evidence and verified. Participants noted that AI-powered systems allow them to “rapidly cross-reference claims,” which helps in “identifying numerical discrepancies and contextual misrepresentations”. The **use of public databases** is also mentioned as a central part of the process, as it allows journalists to “democratise access to disaggregated migration statistics” and enables the “transparent verification of policy implementation and institutional accountability.” One journalist mentioned the importance of open-source platforms, such as OCCRP’s (Organised Crime and Corruption Reporting Project) toolkits, for the “transparent verification of policy implementation and institutional accountability.”

The verification process also extends to visual media. Respondents noted that **digital tools can help to confirm if a photo or video is authentic**. They highlighted the importance of checking images to determine if they were “changed or created by AI” before using them in a story. By adopting these methods, journalists reported that they can make “workflows easier and more reliable” and provide the public with a “data-based overview.”

"I believe that reporting grounded in data collection and analysis can enrich journalism not only by strengthening stories with greater consistency and reliability, but also by generating new questions, story ideas, and lines of inquiry. I tend to believe that combining these tools with strong analytical skills and humanistic approaches can produce truly innovative and impactful content."

Freelance Brazilian journalist covering politics

Analysis of language bias

A second theme focuses on the capacity of machine learning to identify patterns and frames in news stories. One journalist noted that algorithms can "identify linguistic patterns that perpetuate stereotyping or dehumanisation," providing newsrooms with "empirical evidence of framing biases." This support allows journalists to be more precise when "counterarguing on xenophobic and antimigrant statements" by identifying language patterns used by politicians or official sources.

Time management

Most journalists mentioned in their responses how digital tools can assist in managing the speed of the news process. They said that tools make practices of gathering and checking information, transcribing interviews and "searching multiple documents at once" much faster. When using AI for more extensive research, journalists can handle large volumes of data that would take a longer time to be processed manually, possibly conflicting with tight deadlines.

Overall, journalists believe that automating certain tasks can strengthen their work. They suggest that the time saved can be used on other tasks that "increase the quality of the reporting", such as conducting more extensive research, in-depth investigations, and finding more diverse sources.

6.4.3 Challenges of Integrating Digital Tools in News Routines

While journalists acknowledge the benefits of AI and digital tools in reporting, they identify limitations in adopting them in their news routine. Respondents shared that integrating these tools "requires institutional support and resources," which are often a "missing part of news organisations". The responses indicate that the **effectiveness of these tools also depends on the time and training available to journalists**. Respondents remarked that the benefits of digital integration would only be possible "if people get the time to learn using them." There is also a demand for specialised education, with participants stating they "would like for open-source software tools to be more widely taught" across the industry.

"In my country, journalists are still very much attached to a "boomer" version of journalism, where the only thing you can do is speaking to sources. That's not because digital tools wouldn't be of help, but because it's not considered an option due to the "technical" difficulty in using them."

Italian freelance journalist working with community or non-profit organisation

Journalists also raised some concerns, especially in relation to working with AI. They argue that these tools could not support more balanced reporting since "AI is inherently biased" and that without careful use, these technologies "could also open up more problems." Instead, respondents see the importance of using these tools as "assistance" and not as a replacement of journalistic work. They emphasise that while tools can complement the research process, they are not a substitute for it, and "should always be used in addition to other reporting techniques" based on professional standards.

7. Recommendations and Conclusion

This study described factors that influence journalists' reporting, journalists' views on migration coverage and its biases, and their experience and obstacles to using OSINT tools in reporting for verification and investigations. The results of the analysis show that participants regard the work environment as conditioned by editorial constraints contributing to biases, that a lack of workforce diversity also contributes to biased reporting on migration, that ethical and balanced reporting on migration demands very heterogeneous skill sets, and integration of digital tools in news routines, including the time allocated to training.

News organisations need to be aware of the editorial gatekeeping acting as a structural factor for biases emerging independently of individual journalists' own reflexivity. The analysis of news routines indicates that editorial line and time constraints are perceived as the most significant influences in journalists' daily decisions during news work. Editorial gatekeeping is identified as a central factor for biases emerging in news reporting on migration and in determining which stories are covered and get visibility on a given medium's platforms. The influence also extends to the writing process, guiding word choices and terminology used to write a story.

News organisations should account for more diversity in their reporting on migration through a more diverse workforce of different backgrounds: More than half of respondents report relying on sources that are easy to contact or institutionally recognised. They identify time pressure as affecting source choice options. When evaluating the national reporting of migration, respondents are highly critical of similar dynamics they identified in their routines. A majority affirm that the coverage favours official and political voices over the perspectives and narratives of migrants, recognising a limitation on source diversity. Despite the high level of awareness of coverage imbalances, the findings suggest a resistance in journalists' self-perception of bias. Respondents are overall critical of national migration coverage but view their own organisation's reporting as more balanced. A more diverse workforce in newsrooms is regarded as essential by many to provide more diverse coverage of migration, putting migrants' views and perspectives at the centre of news stories.

News organisations should provide training and equip journalists with OSINT techniques to help countering bias. A central finding of this study is the disconnection between the three dimensions analysed, the institutional newsrooms' routines, perceptions of migration coverage, and integration of OSINT and digital tools. While OSINT tools are identified by journalists as useful for verification practices and balanced reporting on migration, most journalists do not have the knowledge to use them. Instead, there is a gap where the use of these tools remains limited and often tied to individually acquired skills. Even when journalists have the expertise, they are sidelined by time constraints and a lack of integration of the tools in news routines. Use of tools and techniques is usually project-dependent, limited to basic tasks and fact-checking, and rarely used to counter structural imbalances identified *and acknowledged* by respondents.

News organisations should make OSINT and digital tools a standard practice and an integrated part of newsroom routines. According to respondents, these skills are often limited to a small number of journalists with specific technical expertise. Newsrooms should provide training for journalists and consider the necessary time to integrate them into existing work routines. It is important to recognise that journalists already work under significant time pressure, which can make it difficult to introduce new steps in the reporting process. However, as respondents pointed out, these tools can increase productivity by saving time when researching, verifying, or processing large amounts of data.

Future research could analyse case studies of newsrooms that have integrated OSINT and digital tools in their news routines. Investigating how these organisations facilitate and resource training and managed work time could be a relevant example for others. Such studies could also examine the

benefits of adopting these tools in relation to audiences' perceptions of trust, reliability and transparency of the news-making process. Understanding the relation between the transparency of these methods in the news, audience trust, and credibility can also be an incentive for newsrooms to adopt these practices to reach audiences that are no longer interested in journalism or have formed polarised views of migration following political rhetoric.

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10. Appendices

A. Appendix 1 - Survey

News Reporting and Verification tools

Start of Block: Introduction

Purpose

This survey explores the main factors influencing how journalists produce news today, in a context of technological change and shifts in how audiences access information. It has four short parts. The first asks general questions about everyday decision-making. The second focuses on the coverage of the migration topic and your perception. The third looks at the digital tools you may use to fact-check your reporting. The final section includes questions about your professional background to help us interpret the results. Your responses are completely anonymous and confidential. The survey takes approximately 10 minutes to complete.

Who we are

This survey is part of DEMINE, a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) networked PhD project funded by the European Commission, involving nine PhDs researching migration, disinformation, and hate speech across Europe. The survey is conducted by Daniela Rebello (Aarhus University) and supervised by Christoph Raetzsch (Aarhus University).

Benefits to you

Journalism plays a key role in supporting democratic debate, particularly when reporting on polarising topics such as migration and hate speech. By sharing your views and professional experience, you are contributing to a clearer picture of how news is produced in different contexts and supporting research to strengthen journalistic methods, training, and quality journalism. Journalists from all areas are encouraged to participate.

Data Processing

All answers will be securely stored and used only for academic research. Data will be stored and processed on Aarhus University servers in compliance with data protection regulations, and the joint data handling agreement of the DEMINE consortium. The results will be presented as combined summaries that do not reveal any individual participant's responses. At the end, you may optionally provide your email if you wish to receive survey results or take part in follow-up interviews. This information will be kept separate from your survey answers to maintain your anonymity.

Funding Information DEMINE is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Doctoral Networks (MSCA-DN), under Grant Agreement no. 101167978. Views and opinions expressed are however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

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End of Block: Introduction

Start of Block: Media bias

Consent

Do you agree on participating in this research?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Do you agree on participating in this research? = No

Display this question:

If Do you agree on participating in this research? = Yes

Part 1 - General (4 questions) This part asks about factors that can influence everyday decision-making as a journalist.

Q1 Which aspects have the most influence on your news reporting?

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
Editorial routines in the newsroom influence which stories and topics are covered. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Editorial priorities mainly influence which stories get visibility or space. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My newsroom's editorial line influences word choices and terminologies. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My personal views mainly influence how I approach and report on a topic. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I tend to rely on sources that are easier to reach or institutionally recognised. (5)	0	0	0	0	0
I adjust my reporting to align with audience interests, engagement metrics, or social media trends. (6)	0	0	0	0	0

Q2 Journalists can often feel challenged with the normative demands of their news work. What aspects do you think influence journalists' reporting?

	Strongly influence (1)	Somewhat influence (2)	Neither influence nor not influence (3)	Slightly influence (4)	Do not influence at all (5)
Personal opinions and experiences on a topic influence how topics get reported and sources are contacted. (1)	0	0	0	0	0
Questions in an interview guide responses in a certain direction. (2)	0	0	0	0	0
Stories are chosen based only on assumptions before fully exploring the facts. (3)	0	0	0	0	0

Q3 How influential do you think a journalist’s personal background (such as economic situation, ethnicity, gender, or sexual orientation) is in shaping how they report a story?

- Not influential (1)
- Slightly influential (2)
- Moderately influential (3)
- Very influential (4)
- Extremely influential (5)

Q4 How important is it for journalists to declare their personal perspectives when reporting on an issue?

- Not at all important (1)
- Slightly important (2)
- Moderately important (3)
- Very important (4)
- It is important, but not allowed (5)
- It is not possible, and it should not be allowed (7)

End of Block: Media bias

Start of Block: Migration bias questions

PART 2 - Migration (3 questions) This part asks about how migration is covered in the news and how you view that coverage. DEMINE explores how journalist see the coverage of migration in order to find ways to support journalism and strengthen democracy and public trust.

Q5 Coverage of migration in the country where I am based...

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
...often focuses on topics such as crimes, border control, or social problems. (1)	0	0	0	0	0
...frequently emphasises economic aspects of migration, such as costs to public services or labour market competition. (2)	0	0	0	0	0
...shows positive contributions of migrants to culture, economy, or community life. (3)	0	0	0	0	0
...portrays migrants without an active voice (e.g., not as direct sources of interviews) (4)	0	0	0	0	0

...focuses more on what politicians say about migration than on the real lives of migrants and their communities.
(5)

0 0 0 0 0

...uses inconsistent or inaccurate terminology (e.g., mixing emigration with immigration, illegal migrants, etc)
(6)

0 0 0 0 0

...has changed over the last years and is now generally balanced, covering many aspects of migration.
(7)

0 0 0 0 0

Q6 How would you describe the way migration is generally covered in your news organization?

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
It is usually balanced, including multiple perspectives from migrants, authorities, experts, and the public. (1)	0	0	0	0	0
Coverage tends to focus on certain dominant themes, for example, security, politics, or the economy, with limited diversity of viewpoints. (3)	0	0	0	0	0
Coverage is mostly one-sided, reflecting a narrow perspective on migration issues, and heavily influenced by parties and politicians. (4)	0	0	0	0	0
Coverage of migration is heavily influenced by discourse on social media. (5)	0	0	0	0	0

Migration is not frequently covered in my news organisation.
(8)

o o o o o

Q7 In your opinion, how should migration be covered in the news?

Q8 Is there anything else you would like to add about migration coverage or this part of the survey? Please use the space below.

End of Block: Migration bias questions

Part 3 - OSINT (5 questions) Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) is the process of collecting, analysing, and verifying publicly available data. Many different tools and softwares can be used in this process. This section explores how such tools are used in your work.

Q9 How much experience do you have with the following OSINT verification techniques?

	No experience (1)	Some experience (2)	Moderate experience (3)	Good experience (4)	Extensive experience (5)
Reverse image searches (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Checking metadata of photos or videos (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consulting public databases (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Google Lens tool (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Google Maps (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tracing geolocation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Web scraping tools for social media (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Crowdsourcing information retrieval (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fact-checking databases (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other: (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q10 How often do you *actually* use these OSINT verification techniques?

	Daily (1)	Weekly (2)	Several times a month (3)	Rarely (4)	Never (5)
Reverse image searches (1)	0	0	0	0	0
Checking metadata of photos or videos (2)	0	0	0	0	0
Consulting public databases (3)	0	0	0	0	0
Google Lens tool (4)	0	0	0	0	0
Google Maps (5)	0	0	0	0	0
Tracing geolocation (6)	0	0	0	0	0
Web scraping tools for social media (7)	0	0	0	0	0
Crowdsourcing information retrieval (8)	0	0	0	0	0
Fact-checking databases (9)	0	0	0	0	0
Other: (10)	0	0	0	0	0

Q11 How important are OSINT verification techniques for your daily news work?

- Not at all important (1)
- Slightly important (2)
- Moderately important (3)
- Very important (4)
- Extremely important (5)

**Q12 What are the main *obstacles* to using verification techniques in news reporting?
(Multiple answers possible)**

- Lack of time (1)
- Lack of training and knowledge of the tools available (2)
- Limited editorial encouragement or institutional support (3)
- Concerns about data reliability or privacy (4)
- Difficulty integrating tools into existing workflows (5)
- I don't find them necessary for my work (6)
- Other: (8) _____

Q13 In your view, how could digital tools (e.g., AI, public databases, open-source software, investigative toolkits) support more balanced reporting?

End of Block: OSINT

Start of Block: Demographics

Q14 In this last part, please answer a few general background questions. Country where you are based

▼ Afghanistan (1) ... Zimbabwe (197)

Q15 Employment status

- Freelancer/Self-employed (1)
- Staff journalist/Full-time employee (2)
- Part-time employee (3)
- Intern/Trainee (4)
- Other (5) _____

Q16 Type of organisation

▼ Local or regional news outlet (newspaper, radio or TV) (1) ... Other (10)

Display this question:

If Type of organisation = Local or regional news outlet (newspaper, radio or TV)

Or Type of organisation = National news outlet (print, broadcast, or online)

Q17 Business model

▼ Commercial broadcaster (1) ... Public service broadcaster (2)

Q18 Size of organisation

▼ 1-10 employees (1) ... Not applicable (e.g., freelancer) (5)

Q19 Your primary reporting focus

- Politics (1)
- Migration/Refugees/Human Rights (2)
- Environment/Climate (3)
- Economy/Business (4)
- Culture/Arts (5)
- Technology (6)
- Local news (7)
- Investigative journalism (8)
- Other (9) _____

Q20 Age

▼ Under 25 (1) ... 55 and above (5)

Q21 Gender

▼ Male (1) ... Prefer not to say (4)

Q22 Years of experience working as a journalist

▼ Less than 1 year (1) ... More than 15 years (5)

Q23 Seniority

- Intern/Trainee (1)
- Junior journalist (2)
- Reporter/Producer (3)
- Senior journalist (4)
- Editor/Managing Editor (5)
- Correspondent (6)
- Freelance journalist (7)
- Other (8) _____

Q24 Do you want to hear about the outcome of this research?

- Yes. Please write down your email: (1)

No (2) _____

Q25 Can we contact you for a follow up interview?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

End of Block: Demographics